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Research Article

“Stability Indicating Liquid Chromatographic Method For The Separation Of Related Substances In Posaconazole Drug Substance And Its Dosage Forms”

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ABSTRACT

A new and simple, rapid, selective gradient liquid chromatographic method was developed for the estimation of related substances in Posaconazole. Good resolution was achieved between Posaconazole and its related substances by using Zorbax RX-C18 250 x 4.6mm, 5 μ m column over a gradient elution comprising mobile phase A (pH 3.0 Phosphate buffer) and mobile phase B (Mobile phase A and acetonitrile in the ratio of 25:75) at 30°C column oven temperature. The USP resolution between the main peak and its impurities was found more than five. Mobile phase flow was fixed at a rate of 1.0 mL/min and elution was monitored at 260 nm. Limit of detection and quantitative of Imp-1 is 0.06 μ g/mL and 0.19 μ g/mL and for imp-2 is 0.05 μ g/mL and 0.18 μ g/mL respectively. The method was validated as per ICH guidelines for accuracy, precision, specificity, linearity,

and sensitivity. Validation studies demonstrated that this HPLC method is stability indicating, accurate, specific, rapid, reliable and reproducible. Linearity was observed for Imp-1 in the concentration range of 0.05– 7.5 μ g/mL and for imp-2 0.05 - 7.50 μ g/mL ($R^2 > 0.95$). The RSD for intra-day and inter-day precision were found to be less than 5%. The percentage recovery was in good agreement and the method is simple, specific, precise, and accurate for the determination of related substances in the pharmaceutical substances and different dosage forms that contain Posaconazole.

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INTRODUCTION:

Throughout the past decades, a significant increase in the incidence of invasive fungal infections has been observed, mainly because of the high number of immunocompromised patients, such as cancer patients, those with acquired immunodeficiency syndrome and haemopoietic stem-cell transplant recipients [1, 2]. The number of agents available to treat fungal infections has increased by 30% since the year 2000. However, differences in antifungal spectrum of activity, bioavailability, formulation, drug interactions and side effects make necessary a detailed knowledge about each drug class [3, 4].

Posaconazole, 4-{4-[4-(4-{(3R,5R)-5-(2,4-difluorophenyl)-5-(1H-1,2,4-triazol-1-ylmethyl)-

tetrahydrofuran-3-yl)methoxy}phenyl)piperazin-1-yl]phenyl}-2-[(1S,2S)-1-ethyl-2-hydroxy-propyl]-2,4-dihydro-3H-1,2,4-triazol-3-one (Fig. 1), is a triazole antifungal drug, approved by the FDA in 2006 and characterized for the broader spectra of action between triazoles, besides the less potential of interactions [3]. It is the first azole agent to demonstrate activity against the zygomycetes, a difficult-to-treat family that includes *Mucor* and *Rhizopus* species [2]. The chemical structures of Posaconazole and its impurities are as shown in 1A-1C

Figure-1A: Chemical Structure of Posaconazole

Figure-1B: Chemical Structure of Posaconazole Impurity-1

Figure-1C: Chemical Structure of Posaconazole Impurity-2

Literature presents some works related to posaconazole assay in biological fluids applying mainly chromatographic methods [5–11]. Kim et al. (2000) [5] validated a reversed-phase HPLC method, using 0.09 M ammonium phosphate monobasic acetonitrile- triethylamine (530:470:0.5 v/v/v) mobile phase for pharmacokinetics studies in dog serum with limit of quantification of 0.05 µg ml⁻¹. In 2003 [6], the same group evaluated the presence of posaconazole active metabolites in human plasma by HPLC and microbiological assay, applying a mobile phase composed of 0.09 M ammonium phosphate buffer (pH 4.5) – acetonitrile-methylene chloride— triethylamine (1060:940:10:1 v/v), a C18 column and 262 nm UV detection for the chromatographic method, and *Candida pseudotropicalis* ATCC 46764 for agar diffusion method. No active metabolite was found. LC-MS/MS methods were also developed [7, 9] to determine posaconazole in human plasma in the concentration range of 5.0 to 5000 ng ml⁻¹. For the first method [7], the chromatographic conditions included a gradient mobile phase program, C18 column and sample ionization by atmospheric pressure chemical ionization (APCI) in the positive-ion mode. For the last method [9], a triple quadrupole equipment and sample ionization using TurboIonSpray® probe in positive-ion mode were used. Both demonstrated to be accurate and sensitive. Considering concomitant analysis of other azoles drugs and posaconazole in human plasma/serum, some works were published using liquid chromatography with UV and MS/MS detection, respectively [8, 10]. The mobile phases were composed of buffers and organic solvents in both cases. Ekiert et al. [11] made a review about the chromatographic and electrophoretic methods applied to azoles determination, including Posaconazole [12-16]. It is possible to observe the small number of works related and the lack of studies about other matrixes than biological fluids [17].

However no method has been published for the estimation of impurities in Posaconazole tablets. The author has tried to develop a simple robust stability indicating analytical method by using HPLC for the estimation of impurities in Posaconazole pharmaceutical substance. In the

present work a simple analytical method was proposed for the estimation of impurities in Posaconazole by using reverse phase liquid chromatographic has been developed and validated as per ICH guidelines [18]. In the present work we developed simple, rapid and accurate reverse phase liquid chromatographic method for the determination of Posaconazole and its impurities.

EXPERIMENTAL MATRIX

Chemicals and reagents

Potassium dihydrogen phosphate, Methanol, Acetonitrile and ortho phosphoric acid was sourced from Merck, All chemicals were of an analytical grade and used as received.

Apparatus

The liquid chromatography systems Waters alliance 2695 separation module with 2998 diode array detector (DAD) has used for method development and method validations. The output signal was monitored and processed by using Waters (Milford, MA, USA) Empower-2 software. Zorbax Rx-C18 (250 mm × 4.6 mm, 5 µm), was used as a column for the separation.

Chromatographic conditions

Related substances/ Impurities separation was achieved on a Zorbax RX-C18 column (250mm × 4.6 mm, 5 µm) by using gradient mode of elution by using mobile A and mobile phase B over a programmable time for 70min. The Mobile phase A was prepared by dissolving 1.36gm of potassium dihydrogen phosphate in 1000mL water, pH of the solution was adjusted to 3.0 by using dilute ortho phosphoric acid solution. The mobile phase B was a degassed mixture of Mobile Phase A and acetonitrile in the ratio of 25:75 v/v. The elution was achieved at a flow rate of 1.0 mL/min. The column oven temperature was maintained at 30°C and the wavelength was monitored at 260 nm. The injection volume was 10 µL with a run time of 70min. A degassed mixture of Acetonitrile and Water in the ratio of 75:25 v/v is used as diluent.

Preparation of Standard Solution and control solution

Standard Stock solution was prepared by dissolving 50mg of Posaconazole drug substance in 100mL volumetric flask, dissolved and diluted to volume with diluent. Working standard solution was prepared by

further diluting 2mL of standard stock solution into 200mL by using diluent. Further A standard sensitivity solution was prepared by diluting 5mL of standard solution to 50mL by using diluent.

Preparation of test solution

Commercially available tablets containing Posaconazole were sourced from local market (n=10) were pulverized with a pestle in a porcelain mortar. The tablet powder equivalent to 100mg drug substance was taken into a 100 mL of volumetric flask, made up to the mark with diluent and the suspension was sonicated for 10-15 min and filtered through 0.45 μ m membrane filters. The filtered solution was injected to LC system.

Method validation

The method was validated (in terms of specificity, forced degradation, sensitivity, linearity, accuracy, precision, solution stability, mobile phase stability, and robustness) in accordance with International Conference Harmonization (ICH) guidelines.

System Suitability

Performed the system suitability by analyzing the standard solution six times and sensitivity solution once as per recommendations given in US pharmacopeia. Calculated the theoretical plates and tailing factor for main peak and S/N ratio for sensitivity solution.

Specificity/Selectivity and Forced Degradation

Studies:

All the individual impurity solutions were prepared and injected at a specification level along with a spiked sample into the chromatograph by using the optimized chromatographic conditions along with diluent as blank.

Similarly forced degradation studies were carried out to demonstrate the stability indicating nature of the developed method by following ICH guidelines.

LOD and LOQ:

LOD and LOQ were termed as the least concentrations of the peaks which can be detected and quantified without any ambiguity in the reporting results. The LOD and LOQ determined by using linearity slope method.

Precision and repeatability:

Method precision was determined by measuring the repeatability (intra-day precision) and intermediate

precision (inter-day precision) of retention times and peak areas for Posaconazole and its impurities. The intra-day variability was performed by the same analyst over one day, while inter-day precision was carried out by another analyst different day. In order to determine the repeatability of the method, replicate injections (n=6) of spiked samples were analyzed.

Linearity:

The linearity evaluation was performed with the spiked standard solutions of (S)-enantiomer at the concentrations ranging from six concentration (n=6) levels from LOQ to 150% (LOQ, 50, 75, 100, 125 and 150%). The %RSD and Y-intercept of the calibration curve (linear regression equation) were computed.

Accuracy:

Recovery experiments were conducted to determine accuracy of impurities by using standard addition method. The study was carried out in triplicate at LOQ, 50%, 100% and 150% levels were performed, The percentage recoveries were calculated.

Solution stability and mobile phase stability:

The solution stability of Posaconazole and its related substances in this method was carried out by leaving spiked sample solution in tightly capped volumetric flask at room temperature (bench top) for 48 h. Mobile phase was also carried out for 48 h by injecting the freshly prepared sample solutions for every 24 h interval. Mobile phase prepared was kept constant during the study period.

Robustness:

To determine the robustness of the developed method, the chromatographic conditions were deliberately altered and verified including the system suitability criteria as per the recommendations given in US pharmacopeia. Established the selectivity factor in all the robustness studies for impurities along with Posaconazole and compared with regular experiment. The flow rate of mobile phase was 1.0 mL/min, to study the effect of flow rate on the peak USP tailing and USP resolution between Posaconazole and its related substances. Flow rate was altered by 0.2 units, i.e, from 0.8 to 1.2 mL/min. The effect of column temperature was studied at 30°C \pm 5°C.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Method Development:

The purpose of current research work was to develop a stability indicating chromatographic method for the separation of related substances present in Posaconazole. The initial method development was initiated by isocratic method by using pH 3.0 Phosphate buffer with acetonitrile in the ratio of 75:25 by using zorbax RX-C18 column over 1.0mL flow rate. Imp-1 was separated from the main compound but Imp-2 was not separated. After few trails, as the separation of impurities was not achieved over isocratic mode, it is switch over to gradient mode of elution. In gradient mode of elution Mobile was A was

used as pH 3.0 buffer (prepared by dissolving 1.36gm of potassium dihydrogen phosphate, pH adjusted to 3.0 with dilute ortho phosphoric acid) and mobile phase B is a mixture of Acetonitrile and buffer (75:25) was used. a time programmable elution was employed and achieved good separation of impurities from main peak without any interference from blank.

Method Validation

System Suitability:

The system suitability solution is prepared as mentioned in the preparation of the standard solution, to obtain a final concentration of Posaconazole 5 $\mu\text{g/mL}$. Similarly, a sensitivity solution was prepared at a concentration of 0.5 $\mu\text{g/mL}$ (Figure 2).

Figure-2 Representative Chromatogram of Blank

Figure-3: Representative Chromatogram of Sensitivity Solution

Figure-4: Representative Chromatogram of Standard Solution

Table-1: Summary of system suitability

Retention time of Posaconazole	Tailing factor for Posaconazole peak	Theoretical plates for Posaconazole peak	S/N Ratio Posaconazole sensitivity solution
17.37	1.0	17970	32.91

Specificity and Forced Degradation:

In-order to prove the specificity and stability indicating nature of the developed method, individual impurities along with spike sample, blank were analyzed by the developed method, there is no blank interference was observed at the retention time of Posaconazole and its impurities. This indicates that the developed method is specific and selective for the estimation of Posaconazole impurities

Further forced degradation studies were conducted as per ICH guidelines by employing different stress conditions such as acid hydrolysis, base hydrolysis, peroxide and thermal hydrolysis. In all the stress conditions, the peak purity for Posaconazole and its impurities were passing. This indicates that the developed method is selective and stability indicating and can be employed for the estimation of related substances in Posaconazole.

*Figure-5: Representative Chromatogram of Un-spiked Sample Solution***LOD and LOQ:**

LOD and LOQ were established by linearity method. LOD and LOQ were estimated to be 0.06 and 0.19 $\mu\text{g/mL}$ for Imp-1 and 0.06 and 0.18 $\mu\text{g/mL}$ for Imp-2 of Posaconazole with good precision at LOQ.

Precision at LOQ was established by calculating %RSD for replicate injections (n=6) of reference standard prepared at LOQ level. The determined LOD, LOQ limit of quantification and precision at LOQ values are reported in Table 2.

Table-2 Summary of peak areas for precision at LOQ

Inj. No	Imp-1	Imp-2	Posaconazole
1	16290	13731	15197
2	16917	13371	15674
3	16807	13125	15142
4	16825	13574	15215
5	17174	13545	15563
6	16569	13613	15374
Mean	16756	13493	15361
%RSD	1.8	1.6	01.4

Figure-7: Representative Chromatogram of LOQ Solution

System Precision:

Performed the analysis of reference solution six times and determine the percentage relative standard

deviation of peak area of replicate injections of Posaconazole.

Table-3: Summary of peak areas of the Posaconazole standard

Injection No	Posaconazole
1	151011
2	152453
3	152152
4	151850
5	152959
6	153271
Mean area	152283
%RSD	0.5

The relative standard deviation observed for Posaconazole are less than 10%.The results comply with the acceptance criteria and indicate acceptable precision of the system.

Method precision

The precision of the method is determined by analyzing a sample of Posaconazole solution spiked with impurities at 100% of the predefined specification limit. The results are tabulated in table no.-4:

Table-4: Summary of results for precision of the method

Inj. No	% of IMP-1	% of IMP-2
1	98.5	94.5
2	99.7	96.7
3	93.9	95.7
4	96.9	96.9
5	97.9	94.9
6	98.7	95.7
Mean (%)	97.6	95.7
% RSD	2.08	0.99

Linearity:

The linearity of the HPLC method was evaluated by injecting standard concentrations of Posaconazole and its impurity samples with a concentration ranging from LOQ to 150%, i.e, 0.05 µg/mL to 7.5µg/mL for Posaconazole, Imp-1 and Imp-2. The peak area response of the impurities and Posaconazole were

plotted versus the nominal concentration. The linearity was evaluated by linear regression analysis, which was calculated by least squares regression method. The obtained calibration curve showed correlation coefficient greater than 0.99 for Posaconazole and its impurities. The results are tabulated (Table no 5A to 5C) below.

Table-5A: Summary of results for Linearity of the method for Imp-1

Name of the level	Imp-1 Concentration			Area Response
	% level	in %	in ppm	
Level-1	log	0.003	0.050	16756
Level-3	50	0.250	2.500	80683
Level-4	100	0.500	5.000	170383
Level-5	125	0.625	6.250	204852
Level-6	150	0.750	7.500	247862
Slope				313041
Intercept				10877
Res sum of squ				6123
CC (r)				0.9984
RSQ (r ²)				0.9968
LOD				0.065
LOQ				0.196
RRF				1.087

Table-5B: Summary of results for Linearity of the method for Imp-2

Imp-2				
Name of the level	Concentration			Area Response
	% level	in %	in ppm	
Level-1	log	0.003	0.050	13493
Level-3	50	0.250	2.500	65215
Level-4	100	0.500	5.000	136574
Level-5	125	0.625	6.250	165309
Level-6	150	0.750	7.500	197673
Slope				250293
Intercept				9128
Res sum of squ				4515
CC (r)				0.9987
RSQ (r ²)				0.9973
LOD				0.060
LOQ				0.180
RRF				0.869

Table-5C: Summary of results for Linearity of the method for Posaconazole and linearity graph

Name of the level	Posaconazole Concentration			Area Response
	% level	in %	in ppm	
Level-1	log	0.003	0.050	15361
Level-3	50	0.250	2.500	74304
Level-4	100	0.500	5.000	157006
Level-5	125	0.625	6.250	189282
Level-6	150	0.750	7.500	227562
Slope				287931
Intercept				10188
Res sum of squ				5557
CC (r)				0.9985
RSQ (r2)				0.9969
LOD				0.064
LOQ				0.193
RRF				1.000

Figure-8: Representative Chromatogram of Linearity Solution at 100% level

Accuracy:

Accuracy for the determination of impurities was performed by preparing spiked samples on drug substance samples at LOQ, 50%, 100% and 150% of the target concentration. The percentage recovery

values obtained for each impurity are in the range of about 95.6-99.8 for Imp-1 and 94.7-99.7, for Imp-2, which are within the specified criteria. The relative standard deviation values of recoveries obtained for all impurities are found less than 2%.

Table-6: Summary of results for Recovery / accuracy of the method

% Level	Imp-1			Imp-2		
	LOQ	96.8	Mean (%)	96.37	98.8	Mean (%)
95.6		SD	0.67	98.7	SD	0.55
96.7		% RSD	0.69	99.7	% RSD	0.56
50%	97.7	Mean (%)	98.43	97.8	Mean (%)	96.73
	99.8	SD	1.18	96.5	SD	0.97
	97.8	% RSD	1.20	95.9	% RSD	1.00
100	97.9	Mean (%)	98.77	96.7	Mean (%)	96.73
	98.6	SD	0.96	98.8	SD	2.05
	99.8	% RSD	0.97	94.7	% RSD	2.12
150	97.8	Mean (%)	97.60	96.7	Mean (%)	97.47
	97.2	SD	0.35	97.8	SD	0.67
	97.8	% RSD	0.35	97.9	% RSD	0.68

Figure-9: Representative Chromatogram of Accuracy Solution at 100% level

Similarly, solution stability, robustness of the method was established and found that the developed method was meeting all the prerequisites mentioned in the ICH guidelines.

CONCLUSION

A simple, sensitive and robust new analytical chiral method has been developed for the estimation of related substances in Posaconazole. The method can be employed for the estimation of the impurities at different stages of drug substance manufacturing, drug substance and its dosage forms. This method has been validated as per ICH and proved for specific. The

proposed method meets the requirements of the all guidelines and is a reliable way to determine the impurities of Posaconazole in bulk drugs and pharmaceutical dosage forms. This method can be used for the routine analysis as well as the stability studies impurity levels in pharmaceutical quality control.

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